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ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period one, written by Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, published by Euclid University, 2019, sets the groundwork for academic writing. A structural approach for essay writing is essential to keep the central question in focus. Whereas the planning of an academic paper should follow basic guidelines, yet it can be varied, referencing has set rules. There are various forms of citation. Referencing other's work is essential to avoid plagiarism and is the crucial component of academic essay writing.

"(A) style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent" (EUCLID 2019, 24). An author may choose a specific writing style; however, consistency is the key. As an example: while one person might write in American English, another may choose British English. As long as the author sticks to one style, the paper is accepted. While following set rules in terms of abbreviating, references, or numbering and dates in an essay, the author should proofread each essay several times, with at least one day in between. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1 introduces the reader to guidelines and rules, accompanied by explicit examples in each section.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Chapter one explains essay writing basics, which brings back memories of the first academic papers I wrote back during my International Baccalaureate. It is essential to be reminded of how to plan and structure an essay. "Structure your essay to communicate your ideas and answer the question" (EUCLID 2019, 3). I remember how my teachers and professors insisted on keeping the research question in mind to avoid

going off-topic. Especially in extensive papers such as a Master's dissertation, this point is crucial. For a doctorate dissertation, this becomes even more important, as this is a comprehensive and lengthy work process. Creative and critical thinking are vital skills to structure an essay properly (EUCLID 2019, 2). I am a visual learner. Hence, mind-maps and highlighters are the best way for me to keep my mind in order. In the beginning, my thoughts are a tangled roadmap. Through a mind-map, I can connect different ideas and structure each thought into paragraphs.

Introduction, body, and conclusions are something I think everyone remembers that has ever attended any educational program that involved essay writing. I believe writers sticking to the useful tip to not start an essay from the beginning, but instead start with the main body, write better papers (EUCLID 2019, 3). Writing an essay is a process that is continually involving and changing. Therefore, initial connections of ideas might change. "Most essays are dramatically improved by careful editing" (EUCLID 2019, 4). During my Master's it helped me to have at least two friends read through my essays. As a German native speaker, I tend to make the same grammatical and structural mistakes. The same applied to my best friend from Norway. So, we were able to help each other. Editing an essay is vital for grammatical errors but also the content. I always try and have a red line and connect each chapter. This red line is only possible through extensive editing at the end.

a) Plagiarism

Back in the day, while writing a doctoral thesis, authors did not have the tools we do today. Tools such as Zotero, which make citing extremely easy, were not available. Referencing the right way is one of the most central skills in academic writing. Part of my Bachelor's thesis was a literature review, compiling relevant information about my research topic by other authors. Citations give authors credit, which I think has something to do with an ethical attitude (EUCLID 2019, 5). Do not claim the ideas of other authors as your own.

"The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote" (EUCLID 2019, 8). I believe the representation of the author's idea can be tricky. It is undoubtedly vital. But I think many times, language can be interpreted differently, especially for non-native speakers. Living and working in a country with another language, I often experience misunderstandings because of language use. With the best intention and an open mind for criticism, I believe this will not become a significant issue. The importance of accepting that one has misunderstood and correcting the mistake cannot be pointed out enough. Being surrounded by native Spanish and English speaking people, I have learned to listen carefully and ask questions. I think the same method should be applied when referencing authors. If there is a vague statement, I would ask a native speaker if my train of thought goes in the right direction.

b) British vs. American English

Another misunderstanding I have experienced is the use of American and British English. Having lived in England for three years, which sets the basics of my English language, I was used to specific vocabularies. "American English is currently the dominant influence on world English" (EUCLID 2019, 27). I was always proud to speak and write British English. The ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period one has taught me differently. American English is more dominant. Having lived five years in the United States for my work, I have learned the differences between certain words and their meaning. However, I never stop educating the American people about vocabularies used in the British language. In my experience, many words are unknown by Americans, mainly due to the factors stated in the ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period one. The media, American cultural influences, the United States' wealth and economic position, and country size are factors why American English is more widespread (EUCLID 2019, 27). For my doctoral, even having my roots in the British language, I decided to remain with the use of American English.

c) Chicago Manual of Style (CMS)

This section of the study material was especially helpful. It reminded me of what to abbreviate, which words to capitalize and when to spell out numbers. Again, drawing back to the first point, consistency is the key. Some forms of abbreviation have two possible ways. Both are accepted as long as the author is consistent throughout the paper (EUCLID 2019, 45).

While writing an essay, careful use of language is essential. Compound words used in different contexts have different meanings. For non-native speakers as myself, this is essential to bring the right idea across. The reader of my paper should understand my trace of thought. When using words in the wrong way, this might create a misunderstanding. Through the P.h.D. being an online taught course only, my writing as to be as specific as it can be. Most of the time, my communication with the professor will only be through response papers or other forms of essays. Hence, it is crucial to make the reader understand exactly what you mean.

3) CONCLUSION

ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period One created the base for what is to come. I think it summarized a lot of information. I was reminded of a lot of information that I had already learned. However, it was a great review, and I learned the right way to use references for my future papers. Since universities use different style guides, this helped me understand what is being asked of me to consider. I will most likely go back to this coursepack and remind myself of specific ways of abbreviating, reference, check my grammatic or make sure I used that compound word the correct way so that there is no

misunderstanding. This coursepack also made me think about and decide to use American English for all futyre papers.

REFERENCES

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